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Direct Infusion Workflow

Overall study design

Title of the study				Influence of obesity and insulin resistance with hepatic steatosis on the human plasma lipidome			
Document creation date		12/16/2025		Principal investigator		Samuel Klein, MD	
Institution		Washington University School of Medicine		Corresponding Email		sklein@wustl.edu	
Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?		Untargeted		Clinical		Yes	

Lipid extraction

Extraction method		2-phase system		pH adjustment		Acetic Acid 1%	
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2-phase system	BUME	Special conditions	Sonication
Were internal standards added prior extraction?	Yes		

Analytical platform

Ionization additives	Ammonium formate, Formic acid	Detector	Mass spectrometer
MS type	Orbitrap	MS vendor	Thermo
Direct type	Syringe	MS Level	MS ²
Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	1.2	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS ²	Low resolution
Resolution at MS ²	Low	Recording mode of raw data at MS ²	Centroid mode
Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No		

Quality control

Blanks	No	Quality control	Yes
Type of QC sample	Commercial sample		

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	Yes	Lipid recovery	Yes
Dynamic quantification range	No	Limit of quantitation (LOQ)/Limit of detection (LOD)	Yes
Precision	Yes	Accuracy	Yes
Guidelines followed	None		

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Available on request	Are metadata available?	Available on request
Raw data upload	Available on request	Additional comments	The data are available upon request from the corresponding author, Samuel Klein (sklein@wustl.edu).

Sample Descriptions

Influence of obesity and insulin resistance with hepatic steatosis on the human plasma lipidome / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min)
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10	Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C
Instant sample preparation	No	Storage temperature	-80 °C
Additives	EDTA		

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) CAR / Lipid identification

Lipid class	CAR	MS Level for identification	MS ²		
Fragments for identification	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Fragment name</td> <td>Carnitine-C4O2H5</td> </tr> </table>			Fragment name	Carnitine-C4O2H5
Fragment name	Carnitine-C4O2H5				
Identification level	sn Position	Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2		
MS ² verified by standard	Yes	Background check at MS ²	No		
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap		
Limit of detection	No	Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)		
Data manipulation	Smoothing	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No		
Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A				

1) CAR / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹				
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Internal standard</td> <td>Endogenous subclass</td> </tr> <tr> <td>CAR 18:0-d3</td> <td>CAR</td> </tr> </table>			Internal standard	Endogenous subclass	CAR 18:0-d3	CAR
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass						
CAR 18:0-d3	CAR						
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No				
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold				
Normalization to reference	Yes	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)				
Batch correction	No						

2) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	TG	MS Level for identification	MS ²						
Identification level	Molecular species level	MS ² adduct	[M+NH4] ⁺						
Fragments for identification	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Fragment name</td> <td>-FA1(+HO)-(NH3)</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>-FA2(+HO)-(NH3)</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>-FA3(+HO)-(NH3)</td> </tr> </table>			Fragment name	-FA1(+HO)-(NH3)		-FA2(+HO)-(NH3)		-FA3(+HO)-(NH3)
Fragment name	-FA1(+HO)-(NH3)								
	-FA2(+HO)-(NH3)								
	-FA3(+HO)-(NH3)								
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes						
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No						
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap	Limit of detection	Signal threshold						
Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)	Data manipulation	Smoothing						
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes						

2) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
TG 15:0/18:1-d7/15:0		TG	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	Yes	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Batch correction	No		

3) DG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	DG	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Molecular species level	MS ² adduct	[M+NH4] ⁺
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
-FA1(-H)-(H2O+NH3)			
-FA2(-H)-(H2O+NH3)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes

3) DG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
DG 15:0/18:1-d7		DG	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	Yes	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Batch correction	No		

4) SE[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	SE	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ² adduct	[M+NH4] ⁺
Fragments for identification			

Fragment name

Cholesterol-C27H45

Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes

4) SE[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹				
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹	<table border="1"> <tr> <th>Internal standard</th> <th>Endogenous subclass</th> </tr> <tr> <td>SE 18:1-d7</td> <td>SE</td> </tr> </table>			Internal standard	Endogenous subclass	SE 18:1-d7	SE
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass						
SE 18:1-d7	SE						
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No				
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold				
Normalization to reference	Yes	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)				
Batch correction	No						

5) Cer[M+HCOO]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Cer	MS Level for identification	MS ²				
Identification level	sn Position	MS ² adduct	[M+HCOO] ⁻				
Fragments for identification	<table border="1"> <tr> <th>Fragment name</th> </tr> <tr> <td>-(+HCOO)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>LCB(-H6NO)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>FA1(-CH2O)</td> </tr> </table>			Fragment name	-(+HCOO)	LCB(-H6NO)	FA1(-CH2O)
Fragment name							
-(+HCOO)							
LCB(-H6NO)							
FA1(-CH2O)							

Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes

5) Cer[M+HCOO]⁻ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹				
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹	<table border="1"> <tr> <th>Internal standard</th> <th>Endogenous subclass</th> </tr> <tr> <td>CER d18:1-d7/15:0</td> <td>CER</td> </tr> </table>			Internal standard	Endogenous subclass	CER d18:1-d7/15:0	CER
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass						
CER d18:1-d7/15:0	CER						
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No				

Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	Yes	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Batch correction	No		

6) SM[M+HCOO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	SM	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	sn Position	MS ² adduct	[M+HCOO]-
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
-(CH ₃ +HCOO)			
-FA1(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes

6) SM[M+HCOO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
SM d18:1/18:1-d9		CER	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	Yes	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Batch correction	No		

7) PC[M+HCOO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	sn Position	MS ² adduct	[M+HCOO]-
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
-(CH ₃ +HCOO)			
-FA1(-H)-(CH ₃ +HCOO)			
-FA2(+HO)-(CH ₃ +HCOO)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No

Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes

7) PC[M+HCOO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
PC 15:0/18:1-d7		PC	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	Yes	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Batch correction	No		

8) PC O[M+HCOO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC O	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	sn Position	MS ² adduct	[M+HCOO]-
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
-(CH ₃ +HCOO)			
-FA ₂ (-H)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes

8) PC O[M+HCOO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
PC 15:0/18:1-d7		PC	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	Yes	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Batch correction	No		

9) PC P[M+HCOO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC P	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	sn Position	MS ² adduct	[M+HCOO]-
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
-(CH ₃ +HCOO)			
-FA2(-H)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes

9) PC P[M+HCOO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
PC 15:0/18:1-d7		PC	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	Yes	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Batch correction	No		

10) PE[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	sn Position	MS ² adduct	[M-H]-
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
HG(PE,140)			
HG(PE,196)			
-FA1(-H)			
-FA2(-H)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes

10) PE[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
PE 15:0/18:1-d7		PE	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	Yes	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Batch correction	No		

11) PE P[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE P	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	sn Position	MS ² adduct	[M-H]-
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
HG(PE,196)			
-FA2(-H)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes

11) PE P[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
PE 15:0/18:1-d7		PE	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	Yes	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Batch correction	No		

12) PG[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PG	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	sn Position	MS ² adduct	[M-H]-
Fragments for identification			

Fragment name
GP(153)
-FA1(-H)
-FA2(-H)

Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes

12) PG[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹				
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Internal standard</th> <th>Endogenous subclass</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>PG 15:0/18:1-d7</td> <td>PG</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Internal standard	Endogenous subclass	PG 15:0/18:1-d7	PG
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass						
PG 15:0/18:1-d7	PG						
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No				
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold				
Normalization to reference	Yes	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)				
Batch correction	No						

13) PI[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PI	MS Level for identification	MS ²				
Identification level	sn Position	MS ² adduct	[M-H]-				
Fragments for identification	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Fragment name</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>HG(PI,241)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-FA1(-H)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-FA2(-H)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Fragment name	HG(PI,241)	-FA1(-H)	-FA2(-H)
Fragment name							
HG(PI,241)							
-FA1(-H)							
-FA2(-H)							
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes				
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No				
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap	Limit of detection	Signal threshold				
Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)	Data manipulation	Smoothing				
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes				

13) PI[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹		
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Internal standard</th> <th>Endogenous subclass</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> </tbody> </table>			Internal standard	Endogenous subclass
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass				

Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	Yes	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Batch correction	No		

14) PS[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PS	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	sn Position	MS ² adduct	[M-H]-

Fragments for identification

Fragment name

GP(153)

-FA1(-H)

-FA2(-H)

Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes

14) PS[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
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Internal lipid standard(s) MS¹

Internal standard

PS 15:0/18:1-d7

Endogenous subclass

PS

Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	Yes	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Batch correction	No		

15) LPC[M+HCOO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPC	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	sn Position	MS ² adduct	[M+HCOO]-

Fragments for identification

Fragment name

HG(PC,224)

-FA1(-H)-(CH₃+HCOO)

-(CH₃+HCOO)

Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes

15) LPC[M+HCOO]⁻ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
LPC 18:1-d7		LPC	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	Yes	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Batch correction	No		

16) LPE[M-H]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPE	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	sn Position	MS ² adduct	[M-H] ⁻
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
HG(PE,140)			
HG(PE,196)			
-FA1(-H)			

Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes

16) LPE[M-H]⁻ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
LPE 18:1-d7		LPE	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold

Normalization to reference	Yes	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Batch correction	No		

17) LPS[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPS	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	sn Position	MS ² adduct	[M-H]-
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
GP(153)			
-FA1(-H)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes

17) LPS[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
PS 15:0/18:1-d7		PS	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	Yes	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipid Data Analyzer (LDA)
Batch correction	No		